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Studies and sport at the University - problems and benefits of sport at University Club

Studia i sport akademicki – trudności i korzyści wpływające z uprawiania sportu w ramach KU AZS

Summary

University Sports Association is one of the most active student organizations in Poland. Most members of the AZS are students who, between the duties of studying, do sports and represent their universities on academic competitions. Sport during the studies required to mobilize the time between the obligations related to learning which is not always easy.

This paper is based on the analysis of an available literature and a research conducted through a questionnaire survey among active members of the AZS University Club at the University of Economics in Katowice. The aim of this article is to answer the question as sports in the Club and activities in AZS effect on school results and developing skills of students.

In the conclusions we presented different effects of sport on academic results, referring both to the amount of time devoted to learning, as well as its quality.

Keywords: AZS, University Sports Association, students, learning, university

Streszczenie

Akademicki Związek Sportowy jest jedną z najprężniej działających organizacji studenckich w Polsce. Większość członków AZS to studenci, którzy, między obowiązkami uczelnianymi, uprawiają sport i reprezentują swoje uczelnie na zawodach akademickich. Uprawianie sportu w trakcie studiów wymaga wygospodarowania czasu między obowiązkami związanymi z nauką, co nie zawsze jest łatwe.

Niniejsza praca jest stworzona na podstawie analizy dostępnej literatury oraz badania przeprowadzonego za pomocą kwestionariusza ankietowego wśród aktywnych członków Klubu Uczelnianego AZS Uniwersytetu Ekonomicznego w Katowicach. Celem artykułu jest odpowiedź na pytanie, jak uprawianie sportu akademickiego w ramach Klubu Uczelnianego i działalność w AZS wpływa na wyniki w nauce i rozwijanie umiejętności studentów.

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We wnioskach przedstawiono różny wpływ sportu na wyniki w nauce, odnosząc się zarówno do ilości czasu poświęconej nauce, jak i jej jakości.

Słowa kluczowe: AZS, Akademicki Związek Sportowy, studenci, uczenie się, szkoła wyższa

1. Introduction

University Sports Association (AZS) is one of the most active student organizations in Poland, bringing together over 50,000 members. Most of them are students, both public universities and private who practice the various sporting discipline between the duties of University and represent their alma mater on academic competitions. Sport during the studies required to mobilize the time between the obligations related with science, which is not always easy.

Sports activities in AZS may be on the one hand an obstacle in achieving good results in learning, because the time dedicated to the sport could be spent on education, on the other hand, allows you to de-stress and improve psychophysical condition of the body, which may be beneficial the quality of the learning.

This work is based on an analysis of an available literature and a research conducted through a questionnaire survey among active members of the AZS Academic Club at the University of Economics in Katowice. The aim of this article is to answer the question as sports university in the Club and activities in AZS affects learning results and development skills of students.

The paper consists of an introduction, theoretical part on the University Sports Association and the AZS University Club of University of Economics in Katowice and the research part, which presents the methodology and test sample, results of the surveys, limitations on the results. At the end of the work there are contains with the answer to the research question.

2. Genesis of University Sports Association (AZS) in Poland

University Sports Association (AZS) is the largest academic organization in Poland, operating in over 300 universities, encompassing over 50 thousand members. Organized in the framework of AZS Academic Championships of Poland and Academic Championship of regions (ex. Silesian Academic Championships) are the base of inter-university competition system. The AZS clubs train both - professional athletes, including Olympians and ordinary students, amateur cultivating their sport disciplines (Wartecki 2008).

AZS was established formally in 1909. The date of constitution of the Association shall be adopted on 15 May 1909., When the Jagiellonian University held a founding meeting (third turn, but the first effective). The development of AZS in the national dimension took place after Poland regained its independence in 1918. Associations, were established in major academic centers of the country. Sports activities has been developed to the outbreak of World War II, when it had to be because of the occupation limited, but not abandoned it completely. They organized,

among others, conspiracy tournaments in different sports. After the war began rebuilding higher education. The structures also rebuilt AZS. But then it adopted the name of the University Sports Association (Akademickie Zrzeszenie Sportowe not the traditional name Akademicki Związek Sportowy). It remains in force until February 1957, when it again became Akademicki Związek Sportowy. In Polish People's Republic AZS was an important part of the national sport. Players of AZS clubs often represented Poland abroad. Not only in the context of competition at the academic level, but also at the level of competitive - at the world championships or Olympic Games. The political transformation has forced University Sports Association for organizational change and re-registration - the Association, and the individual clubs (Hanusz, Korpak 2014). Today, AZS clubs bring together many students and academic workers. In the case of clubs from professional leagues - also professional athletes.

University Sports Association operates in accordance with its statute from 2009. For the purposes of the Association pursuant to Section 7 of the Statute are [Statute of AZS 2009]:

1. Promoting physical culture and tourism, increasing physical fitness and improving the health status of the academic community.
2. Developing competitive sports in the academic environment.
3. Creating activities and development of the sense of co-responsibility for the fate of the parent club, college and the environment.
4. Maintaining the tradition of national development and national civic awareness, and educating members of the Association in accordance with the traditions of AZS.
5. Promoting environmental protection.
6. Promoting the rehabilitation of people with disabilities.
7. Promoting equal opportunities for young people from families with a difficult situation.
8. Action on European integration and the development of contacts and cooperation between societies.
9. Promoting voluntary organizations.
10. Preventing social pathologies, in particular youth addictions threatening learning environment.
11. The promotion and dissemination of Olympism, ideas and education.

AZS primates authorities are: Congress (Pol. Zjazd) - highest authority of the Association), Main Board (Pol. Zarząd Główny), Presidium of Main Board (Pol. Prezydium Zarządu Głównego), Chief Audit Commission (Pol. Główna Komisja Rewizyjna) and the General Court of Arbitration (Pol. Główny Sąd Koleżeński). The organizational units of the University Sports Association are the clubs (university and the environment) and environmental organizations created by the clubs operating in a specific territory. University club operates on the territory of the home university. As a rule at one university can operate an AZS club. It is also possible to create clubs in the departments of subsidiaries of universities. They can obtain legal personality. Then they have its own charter. If you do not have a legal personality, they are binding for them the Statute of AZS [Statute of AZS 2009].

3. University of Economics in Katowice AZS Academic Club – basic informations

University of Economics in Katowice AZS Academic Club (Klub Uczelniany AZS Uniwersytetu Ekonomicznego w Katowicach) operates within the framework of the Environmental Organization (Pol. Organizacja Środowiskowa) of AZS in Katowice. OŚ acting as an association with legal personality. This organization brings together clubs university of Silesia region (Statute of OŚ AZS Katowice 2009).

AZS UE Katowice Academic Club brings together students, graduate students and staff of the University of Economics in Katowice, who are also members of one of the sport swctions of Club (sections of: volleyball, handball, badminton, table tennis, swimming, swimming for the disabled, sport climbing, basketball, mountain biking , bridge, chess, football and ergometer rowing, mountain sports and athletics). A total members of AZS at the University should be 478 people (as at 26.01.2016) and the number of active members of the organization (participating in the activities section of high performance and sporting events) is estimated at about 300 persons. The club also teaches the section of the fitness among others, bachata, salsa, sport aerobics (azs.ue.katowice.pl 2016).

Members of sports sections have the opportunity to represent the University Club as part of intercollegiate competition, as Academic Championship of Silesia and Polish Academic Championship. This rivalry often brings success, both individual and team. An example would be the second place of AZS JE Katowice Academic Club in the overall standings of Polish Academic Championship of social-science university in the season 2014/2015 (AZS ZG, 2016).

The Board of Academic Club is composed of students, members of sports sections of the Club, who through the selection of delegates sections obtained their mandates. Among those involved in the organization and management are also other members AZS who perform their tasks, ad hoc volunteering. Activity in the field of management of the Club allows students to develop many skills are considered to be factors career: creativity, managerial skills in the field of human resource management and technical skills often developed as part of events organized by the Club (Bieda 2006).

Members of AZS at the University of Economics in Katowice that, according to a study of 2015 years (Suchecki 2015), most people (94%), which had already practiced sport, with some of them cultivated a different sport than the one being improved in AZS. Members of of AZS are also generally pleased with the fact of membership. Average grade (where 1 rating was the lowest, and 6 the highest possible grade) in the cited studies was 4.88, and two-thirds of respondents rated their membership on 5 or 6. Only 10% of the players felt that their satisfaction with the fact that membership in AZS is less than four.

4. The method and the research sample

The research was conducted using an online survey form created in Google sent out through the social networking site Facebook to members of the AZS UE

Katowice Academic Club and using paper questionnaires handed out in training sports sections of the Club. Data collection lasted from 3 January to 24 January 2016.

The survey sample was 78 people, and not all respondents answered all questions, so the results presented below, you can see a different number of units surveyed. This means that according to estimates of the number of active members of the organization (300 people) interviewed every fourth athlete (26%). In this case, the unknown size fractions and the 95% level of confidence - the maximum error is 10%. In the presentation adopted as a result of rounding percentages to integers (or 0.5 if deemed necessary). In the case of absolute numbers taken rounding to one (for age) or two decimal places.

The survey involved 31 women (40%) and 47 men (60%). The average age of respondents is 21.5 years, while among women little lower (21.0) than among men (21.7). Dominant - is 20 years of age (23% of respondents), and the median is 21 years.

33 respondents joined the AZS in 2015 (mostly students of the first year of first cycle studies), 19 people in 2014, 10 in 2013, 9 in 2012, 3 in 2011, one in 2010 and two in 2009. One person is a member of the organization longer than since 2009.

Among the respondents were representatives of most of sports sections the University Club. Most were members of the section football and futsal (22 people). Further the athletes of the sections rowing ergometer, mountain sports and athletics (12 persons), badminton (12 persons), swimming (11 people), volleyball (10 persons), table tennis (10 persons), basketball (6), handball (5), chess (3 persons), bridge sports and swimming for disabled people (both - two people), as well as 8 people from AZS activists (some athletes attending classes more than one section, because the sum total is higher than $N = 78$).

The research covered students of all levels and faculties functioning at the University of Economics in Katowice. Most respondents are students first degree (54 persons – 69%). 29 persons (37%) are first year students, 15 people (19%) are second year students and 10 persons (13%) are third year students. Students of second degree accounted for 28% (22 people). 14 persons (18%) are first year students and 8 persons (10%) are second year students. 3% of respondents (2 persons) are graduate students (students of third degree). Of the five operating in the University of Economics in Katowice faculties many people represented the Faculty of Management (29.5%) and the Faculty of Finance and Insurance (also 29.5%). 27% are students of the Faculty of Economics. A smaller group of students of the Faculty of Informatics and Communications (12%). Fifth formed on the university faculty, or the Faculty of Business, Finance and Administration in Rybnik represented by one person (1%).

5. Research results

Students who are active members of the University Sports Association train with varying frequency. Results of research on the number of monthly training sessions to be completed is presented in Graph 1.

Graph 1. Number of trainings in the AZS University Club in a month

Source: own study based on research

On average, members of the sections train nearly five times per month (average - 4.67 - answer over 12 were counted as 13). Dominant and the median is 4. Such an answer was given by 25 respondents (32%). Most of sports sections has classes once a week. Part of the athletes train also more than one section, so more training in a month.

The respondents felt that sports at the University

Graph 2. The feelings related to the effect of sport on school results, N=78

Source: own study based on research

The question about the impact of membership in AZS and participate in activities sports sections on school results refers to the subjective feelings of the respondents and they themselves assessed if the the impact is positive, negative, or consider that it did not exist. As you can see in Graph 2, almost half of respondents (47%) believes that participation in sports has a positive impact on their school results. The opposite view is every tenth person. As many as 42% respondents think that sports activities in no way affect their school results.

Have you ever given up on learning to sport

Graph 3. Resignation from science to sports classes, N=78

Source: own study based on research

More objective was the question of whether study subjects ever resigned from learning (exam, final test, etc.) due to sports activities in AZS sections. That question concerned the facts. More than half of respondents (56%) admitted that at least once be the case. 44% of the players surveyed said they never abandoned the study due to the activities of sports sections of AZS. Graph 3 shows the results summary.

It should be noted that 29 of those questioned (37%) are students first-year of first degree, and the survey was conducted before the winter examination session, so before their first session.

On another question on the number of situations in which abandoned learning in favor sports activities corresponded to only those who answered yes to the previous question, therefore N = 44. Graph 4 shows that for 25% of it was a one-time situation. 34% said that sometimes they did this often, but not more than five times. 10 people (23%) admits that resigned from learning six to ten times. 8 AZS surveyed athletes gave up more than 10 times from learning to sports activities.

How many times have you quit learning for sport activities?

Graph 4. Number of resignation from learning to sports activities, N=44

Source: own study based on research

6. Limitations on the results of research

The survey was conducted on only one university (University of Economics in Katowice). Reference the results to other units of this type in Poland may be possible only having regard to the characteristics of the university, such as profile and number of students. The study was conducted in the period when the University Club was the organizer of the sporting event, which was Chess Polish Academic Championship. Large involvement of members of the Club in the preparation of this event made it difficult to collect data among these persons.

In the case of several sports sections of the Club was researched too few players. Some of them are, in turn, over-represented in this study. Some members of the Club belongs to it for other reasons (ex. ISIC card and personal accident insurance). Such persons are not included in this study.

7. Conclusions of the research

The research shows that only one in ten respondents considers that the involvement in sports activities in AZS may negatively affect its results in learning. Almost half believe that on the contrary and through sports training and coaching have better school results. 42% said that there is no link between their sports activities, and learning outcomes. Please note that the respondents were asked only about their subjective feelings about this phenomenon.

But now another question concerning the fact leaving learning because of sports shows something else. More than half of respondents said that at least once occurred to such a situation. Of the 37 people, who believe that sporting activities in AZS positive effect on their school results, 15 athletes admitted that they happen to opt out of learning to sport. So did the majority (21 of 33) of those who have not seen impact of sport on their learning. All (8 people), who recognized that the impact of sporting activities on science is negative, they replied that sometimes give up of learning in this situation.

It is difficult to accept that resignation from learning for exam or final test may have a positive impact on school results. Despite personal feelings of the respondents, it must be assumed that at least in certain situations sport in the AZS University Club may impair the school results of students, particularly if the abandonment of learning is not a sporadic thing and occurs quite frequently.

However, do not forget about the impact of physical activity on the intellectual abilities of students. Playing sports can positively influence the quality of learning and despite a smaller amount of time devoted to learning, its effects can be improved, which can be emphasized by both the coaches of AZS sports sections, and athletes – students.

Value seems to be also the involvement of students in organizational activities in the University Sports Association. Gained in this way experience (managerial, logistical) in the organization of events and operation of the Club is extremely valuable in further career, especially considering the profile of the University.

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